

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of amino acids by *N*-chloronicotinamide in aqueous acetic acid medium

K. Vivekanandan^{*a} and K. Nambi^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, National College, Tiruchirapalli-620 001, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, St. Joseph's College, Tiruchirapalli-620 002, India

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Kinetics of oxidation of ten α -amino acids by *N*-chloronicotinamide (NCN) in aqueous acetic acid medium in presence of hydrochloric acid have been investigated. The observed rate of oxidation is first order in both [oxidant] and [HCl]. A small increase in rate is observed with increase in [amino acid]. A decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium increases the rate. Addition of nicotinamide (NA), the reduction product of NCN, has a retarding effect on the rate of oxidation. The corresponding aldehydes, ammonia and carbon dioxide have been identified as the oxidation products. Molecular chlorine has been postulated as the reactive oxidising species in the reaction.

Oxidative decarboxylation of amino acids is one of the well-documented biochemical processes. The exact mechanism of the chemical process of oxidative decarboxylation is not well-understood, however, there remains an area for further experimentation. An extensive literature survey reveals that kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of amino acids have been carried out using various *N*-halo compounds¹⁻⁴. Here, we report the results of the kinetic and mechanistic studies of the oxidation of some amino acids with a newly developed oxidant *N*-chloronicotinamide⁵ (NCN) in aqueous acetic acid medium in the presence of hydrochloric acid.

Results and Discussion

The rate laws and other experimental data were obtained for all amino acids investigated. As the results are similar, only representative data are given here. The kinetic results can be summarised as follows.

(i) At constant $[H^+]$ with the [amino acid] in excess, the plot of $\log(E_t - E_\infty)$ (where E_t is the emf of the cell at time t and E_∞ the corresponding value at the completion of the reaction) vs time is linear, indicating a first order dependence of rate on [NCN]. Increase in [amino acid] has a slight positive effect on the rate, indicating fractional order dependence of rate on [amino acid] (Table 1). (ii) The pseudo-first order rate constant increases with increase in [HCl] in the range 0.8–1.2 mol dm⁻³ (Table 2) and plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [HCl]$ is linear with a unit slope indicating first order dependence of [HCl] on the rate of oxidation of amino acids. (iii) The effect of H^+ was investigated in the range 0.8–1.2 mol dm⁻³ of HClO₄ at constant $[Cl^-]$ (0.8–1.2 mol dm⁻³) and the rate increases proportionately with

Table 1. Effect of varying [amino acid] on the rate of reaction

[NCN] = 2×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [HCl] = 0.8 mol dm⁻³, solvent : CH₃COOH-H₂O (1 : 1), [NaClO₄] = 0.6 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 313 K

[Amino acid] mol dm ⁻³	$10^5 \times k_{obs} \text{ s}^{-1}$									
	Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Isl	Ser	Thr	Phe	Asp	Glu
2.0	2.11	2.91	2.30	2.35	3.24	2.82	2.90	3.19	3.17	3.60
3.0	2.48	3.42	2.88	2.82	4.02	3.40	3.28	3.85	3.60	3.94
4.0	2.80	3.88	3.20	3.22	4.73	3.77	3.58	4.34	4.02	4.29
5.0	3.12	4.35	3.52	3.58	5.22	4.17	3.92	4.81	4.36	4.57

Table 2. Effect of varying [HCl] on the rate of reaction

[NCN] = 2×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [Amino acid] = 0.8 mol dm⁻³, solvent : CH₃COOH-H₂O (1 : 1), [NaClO₄] = 0.6 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 313 K

[HCl] mol dm ⁻³	$10^5 \times k_{obs} \text{ s}^{-1}$									
	Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Isl	Ser	Thr	Phe	Asp	Glu
0.8	2.11	2.91	2.30	2.35	3.24	2.92	2.90	3.19	3.17	3.60
0.9	2.34	3.35	2.69	2.70	3.82	3.40	3.25	3.68	3.63	3.97
1.0	2.61	3.77	3.02	3.12	4.22	3.68	3.68	4.13	4.12	4.54
1.1	2.87	4.10	3.40	3.38	4.67	4.15	4.01	4.69	4.56	4.98
1.2	3.11	4.43	3.58	3.69	5.08	4.51	4.39	5.02	4.75	5.52

increase in $[H^+]$ (Table 3). The plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [H^+]$ is linear with unit slope. (iv) The effect of Cl^- on the rate of reaction was also studied by increasing the [NaCl] from 0.8 to 1.2 mol dm⁻³ at constant $[HClO_4]$ (0.8–1.2 mol dm⁻³). It has been observed that the order in $[Cl^-]$ is also one, evident from the linear plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $\log [NaCl]$ with a unit slope. (v) An increase in the rate constant is noticed on decreasing the dielectric constant of the medium (Table 4). Plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/D$ ($r = 0.9900$), where D is the dielec-

Table 3. Effect of varying $[H^+]$ and $[Cl^-]$ on the rate of reaction

 $[NCN] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Glycine] = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, solvent : $CH_3COOH-H_2O$ (1 : 1), $[NaClO_4] = 0.6 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 313 K

$[HClO_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	$[NaCl]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^5 \times k_{obs}$ s^{-1}
0.8	0.8	2.11
0.9	0.8	2.40
1.0	0.8	2.68
1.1	0.8	2.92
1.2	0.8	3.22
0.8	0.9	2.42
0.8	1.0	2.71
0.8	1.1	2.95
0.8	1.2	3.21

rate on the concentration of cyclohexene could not be studied. Another interesting feature is, the ability of the added cyclohexene to stop the reaction as and when it was added to the reaction mixture during the oxidation. Cyclohexene has been used as a chlorine scavenger in the study of deoxygenation of aromatic sulphoxide by thionyl chloride⁶. This lends a strong support to the mechanism involving the formation of molecular chlorine. To establish the formation of elemental chlorine during the course of the reaction some kinetic experiments were carried out with chlorine water and also in the presence of HOCl. The rate constants with both the systems are the same as that of NCN ($k_{Cl_2} 2.1 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$ and $k_{HOCl} 2.1 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$ for the amino acid glycine). The oxidation of all the ten amino acids were studied at different

Table 4. Effect of varying CH_3COOH on the rate of reaction

 $[NCN] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Amino\ acid] = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[HCl] = 0.8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[NaClO_4] = 0.6 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 313 K

CH_3COOH %	H_2O %	D	$10^5 \times k_{obs} s^{-1}$										
			Gly	Ala	Val	Leu	Isl	Ser	Thr	Phe	Asp	Glu	
50	50	37.50	2.11	2.91	2.30	2.35	3.24	2.82	2.90	2.19	3.17	3.60	
55	45	34.75	3.12	3.96	3.43	3.40	4.78	3.98	4.15	4.55	4.47	5.03	
60	40	31.50	5.12	5.53	4.93	5.50	7.75	7.63	7.40	7.67	7.89	7.68	
65	35	28.50	8.97	8.97	7.87	9.35	14.82	15.35	13.40	12.90	14.42	14.42	

tric constant of the medium, gives straight line with positive slopes for different amino acids. (vi) It was found that rate of the reaction decreases on increasing $[NA]$ (Table 5). Thus added nicotinamide has a retarding effect on the rate of oxidation. Further, the plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $[NA]$ is linear indicating inverse dependence of rate on $[NA]$. (vii) Addition of salts like Na_2SO_4 to the reaction medium has no effect on the rate. (viii) A remarkable observation was made when the reaction was studied in the presence of added cyclohexene. A small concentration (0.004 M) of cyclohexene initially added to the reaction mixture virtually arrests the reaction as evidenced by the zero change of potential of the cell constructed. Hence, the dependence of the

temperatures (313–333 K) and the activation parameters evaluated (Table 6).

Mechanism : Addition of nicotinamide decreases the rate of oxidation. This retarding effect suggests that the pre-equilibrium step involves a process in which nicotinamide is one of the products,

If this equilibrium is involved in the oxidation process, the rate should be an inverse function of nicotinamide concentration, which is borne out by the observation that the inverse of the rate constants (Table 5) give a linear plot against $[NA]$ ($r = 0.9910$). Under the experimental conditions studied, five oxidising species Cl_2 , $HOCl$, H_2OCl^+ , $NCNH^+$ and NCN in aqueous solutions are important. The oxidation of amino acids by *N*-chlorobenzamide² and chlorobenzotriazole⁴ has been reported to take place through the intermediate forms of protonated species of the oxidant or molecular chlorine. A similar formulation can also be extended to the oxidation of amino acids by NCN. If $NCNH^+$ is the active oxidant, the reaction must show hydrogen ion catalysis only. Since both hydrogen and chloride ions are found to catalyse the reaction in the present case, we as-

Table 5. Effect of varying $[NA]$ on the rate of reaction

 $[NCN] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Glycine] = 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[HCl] = 0.8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, solvent : $CH_3COOH-H_2O$ (1 : 1), $[NaClO_4] = 0.6 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = 313 K

$[NA]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^5 \times k_{obs}$ s^{-1}
0.0	2.11
1.0	1.83
2.0	1.57
3.0	1.52
4.0	1.41
5.0	1.37

Table 6. Temperature dependence and activation parameters for the oxidation of amino acids by NCN

[NCN] = 2×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [Amino acid] = 2×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [HCl] = 0.8 mol dm⁻³, solvent : CH₃COOH-H₂O (1 : 1), [NaClO₄] = 0.6 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 313 K

Amino acid	$105 \times k_{\text{obs}} \text{ s}^{-1}$					E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	313 K	318 K	323 K	328 K	333 K				
Gly	2.11	4.00	6.14	10.17	14.57	83.3	80.7	104.8	-77.1
Ala	2.91	5.02	6.95	10.47	15.22	70.2	67.6	104.0	-116.3
Val	2.30	3.87	5.24	7.59	9.90	62.4	59.8	104.6	-143.1
Leu	2.35	3.63	5.48	7.87	9.63	62.4	59.8	104.5	-142.8
Isl	3.24	4.48	6.83	9.92	12.53	60.7	58.1	103.7	-145.6
Ser	2.82	4.45	6.55	9.88	12.29	65.0	62.4	104.1	-133.2
Thr	2.90	4.75	7.28	10.00	16.00	72.1	69.5	104.0	-110.1
Phe	3.19	5.17	8.58	12.05	17.12	73.0	70.4	103.7	-106.4
Asp	3.17	5.03	7.43	10.17	14.28	64.5	61.9	103.7	-133.8
Glu	3.60	5.18	7.00	10.88	13.75	59.3	56.7	103.4	-149.1

sume that molecular chlorine acts as the effective oxidant. A simultaneous attack of H⁺ and Cl⁻ ion on the N-haloamide leading to the release of elemental chlorine has been recommended.

Taking into consideration the set of kinetic data presented above and the evidence for the formation of reactive elemental chlorine in the course of the reaction, the following mechanism may be proposed :

This mechanism leads to the rate law (4)

$$\frac{-d[\text{NCN}]}{dt} = k_3 [\text{Complex}] \quad (4)$$

Applying steady state approximation to the complex and the chlorine intermediates the rate law assumes the form,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_1 k_3 [\text{AA}] [\text{NCN} [\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-]}{\left(\frac{k_{-2} + k_3}{k_2}\right) (k_1 [\text{NA}] + k_2 [\text{AA}])} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{NCN}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{Cl}^-] \quad (6)$$

where,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_1 k_3 [\text{AA}]}{\left(\frac{k_{-2} + k_3}{k_2}\right) (k_1 [\text{NA}] + k_2 [\text{AA}])}$$

Equation (5) accounts for first order dependence on [NCN] and [HCl] and fractional order dependence on [amino acid]. It also explains the retarding effect of initially added nicotinamide. Further, it amply rationalises the remarkable observation made with regard to the radical scavenger.

The complex formed in the course of the reaction may be represented in the following way :

Hiremath *et al.*⁴ have suggested the formation of a complex

nine and glutamic acid by N-chloro-benzotriazole. A similar complex has been proposed by Bhargava *et al.*⁷ in the N-bromosuccinimide oxidation of amino acids in aqueous acetic acid medium. This complex has a cyclic structure involving a bromine molecule. On analogy with these two accepted mechanisms, we have ventured to suggest the formation of the complex with the structure given above. The rate-determining step proposed in the above mechanism predicts negligible salt-effect which has been experimentally observed. The formation of the complex involves the charge separation which points to a negative solvent effect. This has been confirmed by the increase in rate with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. The involvement of amino acid molecule in the rate-determining step leads to different values of k_{obs} for different amino acids investigated.

The proposed mechanism is well supported by the moderate values of energy of activation and thermodynamic parameters (Table 6). Although these parameters are composite values arising out of different k values they are of the right magnitude. High positive values of the free energy of activation and the enthalpy of activation indicate that the transition state is highly solvated, whereas the negative entropy of activation indicates that the transition state is highly solvated and the activated complex is more rigid. The activation enthalpies and entropies of oxidation of all the amino acids are linearly related ($r = 0.9943$), implying that all the substances undergo oxidation by the same mechanisms.

Experimental

The amino acids (A.R., Loba) were used as such. Standard solution of NCN (m.p. 222°) was prepared afresh in water and its purity was checked iodometrically. Hydrochloric acid (AnalaR) was used as source of hydrogen ions. Sodium perchlorate (Merck) was used to keep the ionic strength constant. Acetic acid (A.R., Qualigen) was purified by standard method. Conductivity water was used throughout the study. Other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

The reaction was carried out under pseudo-first order condition ($[\text{amino acid}] \gg [\text{NCN}]$). The reaction was followed potentiometrically by setting up a cell made up of the reaction mixture into which the platinum electrode and reference electrode (SCE) were dipped. The emf of the cell was measured periodically using a Equip-Tronics (EQ-DGD) potentiometer, while the reaction mixture was continuously stirred. The pseudo-first order rate constants computed from the plots of $\log (E_t - E_\infty)$ against time were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : A mixture of amino acid (0.01 mol dm^{-3}), NCN (0.05 mol dm^{-3}) and HCl (0.8 mol dm^{-3}) was made upto 50 ml with water and acetic acid mixture (1 : 1). After the reaction was complete, the excess of NCN was determined iodometrically, and several determinations with various amino acids indicated 1 : 1 stoichiometry. The overall stoichiometry of the oxidation reaction may be represented as

In a typical experiment, a mixture of glycine (3.7 g, 1 mol

dm^{-3}) and NCN ($1.5 \text{ g}, 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was made upto 50 ml with acetic acid-water mixture (1 : 1) in presence of HCl (0.8 mol dm^{-3}). The mixture was allowed to stand for 12 h in the dark to ensure completion of the reaction. It was then treated with an excess (125 ml) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in HCl (2 mol dm^{-3}) and set aside for 10 h. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, recrystallised from ethanol, (80%). The product was found identical (m.p. and m.m.p.) with an authentic sample of DNP of formaldehyde. In similar experiments with other amino acids, the corresponding carbonyl compounds were identified as their DNP derivatives. In all the cases carbon dioxide and ammonia were detected by baryta water and Nessler's reagent respectively. The presence of corresponding aldehydes and ammonium ions were also confirmed by the spot tests⁸ with chromotropic acid and *p*-nitrobenzenediazonium chloride respectively.

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